

A global database of public agricultural R&D investment: 1960-2022

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Abstract Investment in public agricultural R&D is a key driver of agricultural productivity, which is regarded as one of the major solutions to enhance global food security, reduce the environmental impact of agricultural production and enhance crop resilience to climate change. Detailed information on public agricultural R&D investment is required to inform national science and technology policies that aim to improve the performance of the agricultural sector and monitor whether countries are on track to reach (inter)national targets. Due to the long lead-time, it requires exceptionally long time-series to assess the impact of public agricultural R&D spending on present and future agricultural productivity. To address these issues, this paper presents GRAPE - the WUR-ERS Global Research on Agriculture: Personnel & Expenditures database, which contains data on the number of public agricultural researchers and R&D expenditures for 190 countries, broadly covering the period 1960-2022. To construct the database, information from a large number of sources was combined, different R&D classifications were harmonized and missing data were imputed.

Background and summary

Increasing agricultural productivity is regarded as one of the main solutions to raise food production and reduce the environmental impact of agricultural production¹. A large body of studies has shown that public investments in agricultural R&D are an important driver of agricultural productivity growth. A meta-analysis found internal rates of return between 34% and 42% for high- and low-income countries, respectively². Due its high potential to contribute to global food security, increasing the investment in agricultural R&D is one of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2 targets, to achieve zero hunger in 2030. In addition to boosting productivity growth and agricultural production, investment in R&D is also essential to develop crops and farming practices that are resilient to climate change, particularly in low-income countries, where a large part of the population depends on agriculture for a living³.

Detailed information on public agricultural R&D investment is essential to inform national science and technology policies that aim to improve the performance of the agricultural sector. International comparable data will help analysts and governments to compare agricultural research investments with those of other countries and support monitoring whether countries are on track to reach (inter)national targets.

Although institutions such as the CGIAR, EUROSTAT and the OECD, have systematically collected agricultural R&D statistics for low, middle and high-income countries, their efforts have a strong regional focus, resulting in fragmented data sets that only cover a limited number of countries and are not always directly comparable. Moreover, they do not always contain long-run time-series. Many studies point out that the period between the start of research on agricultural technologies and when resulting innovations are adopted and improve productivity may span between 35 to 50 years⁴. Hence, it requires equally long time-series to investigate the impact of investment in agricultural R&D on improvements in agricultural productivity.

Several researchers have attempted to overcome these issues by combining and harmonizing national statistics to construct a global database of public agricultural R&D investment^{See 5 for a review}. The first initiative to create such a database was undertaken by⁶, who collected data on R&D spending and personnel for 30 countries from the 1950s to the early 1970s. Updates and revisions of this study are⁷ and⁸. In 1980s the International Service for National Agricultural Research (ISNAR) was launched, which aimed to systematically collect and standardize international information on public agricultural R&D expenditure and personnel. Key outputs were⁹ and¹⁰ that present internationally comparable data with public agricultural R&D statistics for 154 countries spanning the period 1960-86. In the 1990s, ISNAR transitioned to the Agricultural Science and Technology Indicators (ASTI) initiative, led by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) (but discontinued in 2023), which mainly focused on the collection of international comparable agricultural R&D statistics for low- and middle-income countries but regularly compiled global estimates^{11,12}. Another initiative to compile a global database of international agricultural R&D statistics is the InSTePP International Innovation Accounts: Food and Agricultural R&D data series compiled by the International Science & Technology Practice & Policy (InSTePP) center at the University of Minnesota^{13,14}. The latest version⁵ includes private and public agricultural R&D expenditure data for 158 countries, spanning the years 1960 to 2011, although this database does not publish annual time series by country.

Despite the long history of creating global databases and overviews of public agricultural R&D investment, the existing data sets are largely outdated now and often not available in the public domain, which limits their usefulness to inform evidence-based policy making. To address this gap, this paper presents GRAPE - the WUR-ERS Global Research on Agriculture: Personnel & Expenditures database that contains international comparable data on the number of public agricultural researchers and R&D expenditures for 190 countries, broadly covering the period 1960-2022.

The GRAPE database makes three contributions to the previous agricultural R&D data collection efforts. First, it

extends the country coverage to 190 countries, covering 99.7% of global GDP and 99.6% of agricultural GDP, and updates the time-series to the recent past. Second, it presents complementary time-series on the number of researchers, which is an indicator of the human resource commitment to public investment in agricultural research⁹. Although reported by international initiatives, such as ASTI, EUROSTAT and OECD, previous attempts to construct a global database on public investment in agricultural research¹⁰ have not included an indicator of research staff. Finally, it tests and adopts a consistent approach to handle missing information, which is a major issue for any effort to construct a global resource with public agricultural R&D data that involves combining ‘patchy’ information from a large number of different sources.

Preliminary versions of the GRAPE database have been used in^{15, 16, 17} and¹⁸ to analyse global patterns of investment in public agricultural R&D and its impact on agricultural productivity, food security and climate adaptation. This paper presents an updated version that includes a larger number of countries and more recent information as well as detailed documentation on the construction of GRAPE, sources and the approach used to deal with gaps in the data.

Methods

Concepts and definitions

For our definition of ‘public agricultural R&D’, we relied on the OECD Frascati Manual¹⁹, which provides guidelines for the collection of research and development statistics (Supplementary Section A lists the key concepts and definitions that are relevant for this study). Public R&D is the total of R&D undertaken within two performing sectors: government (e.g. local, state and national institutions) and higher education (e.g. universities and related research institutes).

Agricultural R&D refers to primary agriculture, fishery and forestry research. In practice primary agriculture (i.e. crop and livestock) research makes up the largest share although there are notable exceptions such as Sweden and Iceland where forestry and fishery make up the largest part of agricultural GDP²⁰. We followed⁹ and²⁰ and attempted to define research by purpose i.e. the socio-economic objective of the research program or project (e.g. agricultural productivity in case of improving the fuel efficiency of agricultural equipment), rather than its content (improvements in energy use in the aforementioned example). This approach is preferred because it captures the R&D activities that potentially contribute to agricultural output and productivity growth, and is therefore the most relevant measure to inform agriculture sector R&D policies. The OECD socio-economic objectives (SEO) classification, which includes a category Agriculture, is a widely used system to categorize research by purpose.

Another option is to classify research by field of science, which refers to the nature or the knowledge domain of the activity. This is done by the OECD Fields of research and development (FORD) classification, which includes a category: Agricultural and veterinary sciences. Due to the nature of activities, most countries use socio-economic objective classifications to allocate government R&D, while field of science classifications, such as FORD, are preferred for the R&D performed by the higher education sector.

In practice, it is not straightforward to implement socio-economic and field of science classifications consistently as there are ambiguities within socio-economic sectors and fields of science classes, which means research activities could be allocated to multiple categories^{see section 12.4 in 19}. Also countries tend to use variations of the SEO and FORD classifications and even might use different systems across performing sectors and indicators (i.e. expenditure and human resources). Where possible, we preferred the socio-economic objective over field of science classification when both types were available.

We included two indicators of public agricultural R&D. The first one is R&D spending (RD), expressed in 2017 PPP\$ values (but we also provided values in local currency units (LCUs) and US\$). This measure is commonly reported in inter(national) studies and reports that analyze investment in agricultural R&D. It is also a key statistic to assess the extent to which public investment contributes to an increase in agricultural (total factor) productivity^{15,21,22}. In addition, we also compiled time-series on the number of researchers expressed in full time equivalent (HR) that are employed by public agricultural research entities. Alongside R&D spending, this indicator provides additional insights on the level of agricultural research capacity and commitment per country¹⁰.

Construction of database

A schematic overview of the steps involved to construct the GRAPE database is presented in Figure 1. It involves four steps: (1) Data collection; (2) Data pre-processing; (3) Data linking and imputation and (4) Manual inspection and adjustments, which are discussed in the sections below.

Figure 1: Steps to construct the GRAPE database.

Step 1: Data collection

The first step in the creation of the GRAPE database was the systematic collection of data on RD and HR per country for the period 1960-2022. We started by gathering data from several ‘core’ initiatives, which we considered as the most detailed and reliable sources of national agricultural R&D statistics: ASTI (for low- and middle-income countries) and OECD and EUROSTAT (for high-income countries). In addition, we gathered data from other international and regional initiatives that present global (UNESCO) and regional (RICYT for middle- and Latin American countries) information.²³ also provides information on RD but only reports government budget allocations for agricultural R&D (GBARD), which reflects expenditures by government funding agencies, which may go to public or private research performers, and excludes non-government sources of funding for public research institutes. An in-depth analysis showed that GBARD is a poor predictor of actual spending (see Supplementary Section B). We therefore decided to only use this type of data when no other sources of information were available and when trends seem in line with additional information on RD and/or HR trends for periods with overlapping information.

For data before 1980, which is not covered by most of the aforementioned sources, we took information from^{6, 9, 10} and ISNAR country briefs (various). For countries, for which data was still missing or with limited coverage, we (a) consulted publications and websites from national statistical offices, building on the data presented in²⁰ and (b) collected information from scientific and grey literature, informed by earlier efforts of research team members to compile a global public agricultural research data set^{12,15}. Table 1 provides an overview of all sources used. Finally, for ten countries (See GRAPE documentation), we found data spanning the pre-1960 period that for some countries even goes back to the end of the 19th century, which we also added to the database.

Table 1: Overview of GRAPE data sources. HR and RD refer to number of public agricultural researchers and R&D expenditures, respectively.

Source	Coverage	Time period	Indicators	Note
ASTI (2014, 2017, 2024, 2024a)	Low- and middle-income countries	1981-2021	HR & RD	Discontinued
EUROSTAT (2024)	EU27 and several other countries	1980-2022	HR & RD	
FAO (2024)	Global	2001-2022	GBARD	
OECD (2024)	OECD member countries	1980-2022	HR & RD	
UNESCO (2021)	Global	1996-2018	HR & RD	Discontinued
RICYT (2024)	Central and Latin America	1996-2022	HR & RD	
ISNAR country briefs (various)	Low- and middle-income countries	1960-1992	HR & RD	Discontinued
Boyce & Evenson (1975)	Global	1950-1974	HR & RD	Not always comparable
Pardey & Roseboom (1989)	Global	1960-1986	HR & RD	
Pardey et al. (1991)	Global	1961-1981	HR & RD	
Heisey and Fuglie (2018)	High-income countries	1960-2013	RD	
National statistics (various)	Global	Varies	Varies	
Literature (various)	Global	Varies	Varies	

To support the harmonization of units and the imputation procedures (see below), we created a complementary global database with macro-economic information for the period 1960-2022. Key data series in the database include implicit GDP deflators, purchasing power parity (PPP) conversion factors, agricultural GDP series and agricultural output statistics. The main source of the deflators was the²⁴, which offers, depending on the country, macro-economic time-series from 1960 onward. For countries, with incomplete or missing data, we took complementary information from the²⁵ (since 1970) and²⁶ (since 1980), which also provided GDP deflator time-series information. A comparison between countries, for which all three data sources include information, showed little if any difference. We used historical data from⁹ to backcast the deflator series of some countries to 1960 using the annual rate of change. PPP conversion factors were taken from²⁴ and extended with similar information from²⁶ for a few countries that were still

missing. Finally, we compiled time series on agricultural GDP, which were taken from²⁵, and agricultural output, which were obtained from²⁷.

Step 2: Data pre-processing

After the data collection step, we processed the raw data to create international comparable series. In particular, we addressed the following issues:

- *Standard definition of public agricultural R&D.* As explained above, countries may classify public agricultural research activities by socio-economic objective, our preferred measure, or field of science. In case we collected primary information from national statistics (e.g. China and Canada), we tried to collect data by socio-economic objective. Similarly, in case data was taken from EUROSTAT and OECD data sets, which sometimes report data using different classifications systems for the same country (also see below), we selected the socio-economic objective series.
- *Harmonization of units.* First, we converted all current RD statistics in LCUs to 2017 PPP\$ values, applying the recommended ‘first deflate, then convert’ approach²⁸. A few, mainly historical sources, presented data in constant PPP\$ values but with an older base year than 2017. We rebased these to 2017 PPP\$ using relative PPP conversion factors if PPPs for the older base year were available. In other cases we used the US GDP deflator. Second, where needed, we converted HR in head count (HC) units to FTE. For the conversion, we used data from²⁹, which, for a selection of countries, presented data both in HC and FTE units. These conversion factors were subsequently applied to countries with similar levels of economic development to derive the number of researchers in FTE. In other cases we applied growth rates in HC series to backcast recent data in FTE.
- *Integration of EUROSTAT and OECD statistics.* Both the EUROSTAT and OECD databases provide detailed information on research activities by performing sector for European countries using similar classifications systems. A close comparison showed that, although the statistics are nearly identical, longer time-series can be generated by combining data from both sources. For this reason, we integrated the statistics into one database (referred to as EUROSTAT & OECD in the database). In case of inconsistencies, we used EUROSTAT data for the European countries. We applied several simple imputation techniques to deal with missing data, such as using the growth rate of FORD statistics to extrapolate missing SEO data. In rare cases, we also used RD trends to extrapolate HR, and vice versa.
- *Handling of missing data and quality control.* Depending on the source and country, occasionally we found one to three year data gaps within the time series. We imputed missing values assuming a constant exponential growth rate (see next section). In rare cases, we omitted or adjusted (i.e. in case of obvious data entry errors) extreme values, which we considered as implausible. We applied exponential interpolation in case this resulted in data gaps.

Step 3: Data linking and imputation

In the final step, we linked the data from different sources to create consistent long-run time series of RD and HR, and imputed remaining missing values.

As mentioned above, dealing with missing information in public agricultural R&D statistics is a major issue that needs to be tackled in order to create long-run continuous time-series. Most previous studies have applied basic techniques, such as linear interpolation and back- and forward casting using the rate of change in agricultural GDP (also referred to

as agricultural research intensity (ARI), which is the ratio of RD to agricultural GDP)¹³. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies, which systematically investigated, the performance of these and other techniques to impute missing data in agricultural R&D statistics. To select the best-performing approaches, we conducted an in-depth assessment and comparison of techniques (see Supplementary Section B). The assessment established that an ensemble approach in which different imputation results are averaged provided the most accurate results. This is in line with the literature on forecasting, where ensemble approaches are also recommended³⁰. This resulted in the following approach to handle missing data.

First, for each country, where possible, we spliced all data by using growth rates and information in overlapping years. As a rule, we started with the most recent statistics and worked backwards in time to splice all data together. The exception to this procedure was when ASTI and EUROSTAT-OECD, which we considered as the most reliable data sources, did not include the most recent information. In such cases, we spliced ASTI/EUROSTAT-OECD data forward using information from, for example FAO, RICYT and national statistics, which sometimes included more up to date statistics. Before merging the different data sources, we closely inspected all the available series for each country and discarded series which were deemed implausible or inconsistent.

Second, we applied several methods to deal with missing information that remained after splicing the data together. We distinguished between three different types of missing data, which were each treated differently (Figure 2):

- *Data missing within time-series*, i.e. when both older and newer data were available, with a data gap in the middle. To impute this type of missing information, we applied simple exponential growth rate interpolation (EI) as this approach showed superior performance over ARI imputation and more advanced multiple imputation techniques³¹, both of which require auxiliary data (e.g. agricultural GDP and other covariates) that are not always available for historical periods (Supplementary Section B).
- *Data missing for recent years*, i.e. when data is missing between the year of the latest observation and 2022. For a large number of countries data for HR and RD were not available for the most recent one to five years. The main reason for this was that databases such as EUROSTAT and OECD were not always fully up to date, whereas others, such as ASTI and UNESCO, were discontinued and therefore did not contain the most recent observations. To impute these values, we used an ensemble approach, which takes the mean of different imputation methods. Where possible, we combined the following imputation approaches: (a) Extrapolation of data using the growth rate of agricultural GDP (AGGDP); (b) Extrapolation of data using the growth rate of agricultural output (AGOUTPUT); (c) Extrapolation using the growth rate of RD or HR, when information on one of them was more complete than the other; (d) NAIVE forecasting, in which the last observation is carried forward; and two common time-series forecasting approaches: (e) simple exponential smoothing (SES), which is the preferred method for stationary data with no clear trend, giving more weight to recent observations; and (f) Damped Trend (DT), which works best for data with a (long-run) trend³². SES and DT require around 10-20 observations to create reasonable forecasts and therefore were only applied in case 15 original data observations were available.
- *Data missing for distant years*, i.e. when data was missing between 1960 and the first year of observation. This problem mostly occurs for former USSR and several Eastern European countries, for which data collection started around 1990 and data for previous decades is frequently missing, as well as for a handful of countries that are not covered by⁹ and ISNAR country reports. Unless, additional information on HR/RD is available, we decided not to impute data missing for distant years.

Figure 2: Decision tree for imputation of missing data. Note that for a few, mostly small-island economies AGGDP or AGOUTPUT data was not available and therefore only one of the related imputation techniques was applied.

Step 4: Manual inspection and adjustments

After the data linking and imputation step, we manually inspected the results to see if it resulted in extreme values and implausible rates of change. We also took into account the expected negative impact of conflicts and wars on the investment in public agricultural R&D. For several countries, we decided to remove the AGGDP based imputation from the ensemble because of extreme fluctuations in the AGGDP series, resulting in unrealistic imputations. We also manually adjust the HR and RD series for Solomon Islands to very low levels following an episode of civil or communal violence that severely impaired the national agricultural R&D system (see GRAPE documentation).

Coverage

The core of the GRAPE database broadly covers the period 1960-2022. However, depending on data availability actual intertemporal coverage per country might differ. Figure (3) depicts the number of countries per year for which information (including imputed) is available in GRAPE. For ten countries, we managed to add HR (only one country) and RD information for the pre-1960 period. For the majority of countries the first year of data is 1960 (74) and 1961 (83), respectively. Most of the remaining countries, with shorter time-series are former USSR economies, located in the Europe & Central Asia region for which statistics are only available from 1990 onward. Another group of countries with incomplete data are small island nations, located in the East Asia & Pacific region.

Figure 3: Coverage of GRAPE by region and over time. The figure shows the number countries for RD data is included between 1888 and 2022. HR information is only included after 1960 for each country and year, except for South Africa for which RD and HR data are available from 1910 to 2022.

Figure 4 provides an overview of (weighted) share of observations per source for HR and RD for each decade. The figure shows that data coverage is very high in the period 1960-79, resulting in a relatively low share of imputed values. This is mainly due to the extensive data collection efforts of the, now defunct, International Service for National

Agricultural Research (ISNAR)^{9,10}. For the period 1980-2019, much less observations are available as indicated by share of 36-57% imputed values. However, the share of imputed values weighted by R&D spending is much lower because information is predominantly missing for small countries. This is not the case for HR, where data for India and China were often not available, resulting in a high imputation share. For the most recent period (2020-22), data is largely incomplete because of the discontinuation (e.g. ASTI and UNESCO) and limited updating (e.g. EUROSTAT, OECD and FAO) of international data collection efforts.

There are also stark regional differences in data availability and the share of observations that was imputed (Figure 5). Data coverage for both HR and RD is generally high for North and South-America, South Asia and a selection of African countries, while for Europe, parts of Asia and Oceania only RD information was identified. In contrast, for a number of African countries and most of the former USSR economies, only a limited number of data points are available, resulting in a high share of imputed values.

Figure 4: Summary of data sources by decade and indicator. Share of imputed (a) RD and (b) HR values. Imputed refers to all observations that were imputed using one of the approaches described in the text and indicated by one or more of the following codes: ei, i_aux, i_naive and, i_ens and i_man (Table 2 and Table 3)

a

b

Figure 5: Geographical distribution of the share of imputed observations for (a) RD and (b) HR per country. The share of imputed observations is calculated by dividing the number of imputed observations by the sum of number of observed and imputed observations, as such accounting for the relative short time-series of certain countries (e.g. former USSR).

Data records

The GRAPE database and supporting information is available on Zenodo at the following repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15081424>³³. The repository includes several data files. The main data file (`grape_db_[version].xlsx`) contains the HR (FTE) and RD (2017 PPP\$) data series from the first year data was available to 2022. The data file includes (a) two columns to identify the country (country name and the corresponding ISO three character code); (b) year, variable (HR or RD) and unit columns; (c) a column with a short reference to the data source; (d) a column with a code to describe the adjustments to the raw data (e.g. treatment of extreme values and missing data - see Usage notes); and (e) a column with a code to describe the data linking and imputation approaches (see Usage notes). The `rd_db_[version].xlsx` file presents RD in 2017 PPP\$ values (identical to the main data file), constant 2017 LCU and constant 2017 US\$. The `hr_pre_imp_[version].rds` and `rd_pre_imp_[version].rds` file contain the HR (FTE) and RD

(2017 PPP\$) series before imputation in the R³⁴ data format. The Zenodo repository also contains three auxiliary data files, which present tables for LCU to 2017 PPP\$ conversion factors (`ppp_2017_db_[version].rds`), LCU-USD exchange rates (`xr_2017_db_[version].rds`) and the macro-economic database (`macro_db_[version].xlsx`). Finally, the repository includes a pdf document with detailed country level documentation, explanation of codes and the full reference list of data sources.

Technical validation

Manual validation and adjustments

During various steps to construct the GRAPE database (Figure 1), we undertook actions to inspect, validate and, where needed, correct the data. In step 2, we manually inspected the raw data for outliers, implausible patterns and missing information. Examples of such errors include zero values, where a missing value would be most logical, the extrapolation of period averages to individual years, and obvious data entry mistakes (e.g. misplacement of the decimal separator). Depending on the problem, we omitted the observation and replaced it using our imputation procedure or corrected the error.

When splicing the data from different sources (step 3), all available time-series were visually inspected country by country. In case of unexpected or contradicting trends between different data sources, the country series were discussed with the research team and a joint decision was taken on which sources to use and how to process and combine the available information. For several countries, we decided not to use the²³ GBARD data because the pattern was regarded as too volatile and not in line with ASTI and EUROSTAT-OECD databases, which were regarded as the most consistent and reliable.

In step 4, we used two simple metrics to validate the consistency of the HR and RD series. First, we inspected the distribution of R&D spending per researcher (i.e. RD divided by HR) across broad regions. Although, differences across countries and regions were expected, 2017 PPP\$ per FTE should be broadly comparable between countries in the same stage of economic development. Second, we calculated the ARI for each country and year. Also here, it was expected that the share of R&D expenditures in agricultural GDP was within a comparable range. We closely inspected that country series with extreme values and, where appropriate adjusted outliers or discarded raw data sources with extreme values.

Finally, the HR and RD data series for each country were manually inspected by the research team, some of which have considerable experience with constructing and analyzing long-run public agricultural data sets. As described above, for a few countries, the imputations were considered as unrealistic and adjusted accordingly. All actions to adjust the data were given a code in the main data file and were summarized in the GRAPE documentation.

Comparison with alternative database

We validated the GRAPE database by comparing it with a comparable data set presented in¹⁴, which analysed global patterns of public and private agricultural R&D spending using the latest version of the InStePP International Innovation Accounts: Food and Agricultural R&D database⁵. Unfortunately, the annex of the paper includes only a subset of the global InStePP database, which has not been made public and therefore a detailed comparison was not possible. Nonetheless, the available data can be regarded as a good proxy because it covers six years spanning the period 1980-2011 and 20 countries, including various low-, middle and high-income economies.

We found a very high correlation (0.96) with the InSTePP data set (Figure 6). This is not surprising as for a large number of countries, both the databases relied on the same international efforts to collect agricultural R&D expenditure information (e.g. ASTI, EUROSTAT and OECD) although methods to process, harmonize and impute the data might be different. Only for Iran (IRN), the GRAPE database includes several observations that are somewhat lower than those in the InSTePP database. The most likely reason for this is that we integrated new data from³⁵, which were not used in the InSTePP database.

Figure 6: Comparison between GRAPE agricultural R&D expenditures and InSTePP database presented in¹⁴ (20 countries, 6 periods). For comparison, InSTePP data expressed in 2009 PPP\$ values were converted to 2017 PPP\$ values using the US GDP deflator from²⁴.

Usage notes

Despite our efforts to create an internationally comparable data set, the GRAPE database is not without limitations. First, countries use a variety of classification systems to measure the size of investment in public agricultural R&D, including socio-economic objective and field of science approaches. We made an effort to harmonize the data series, use consistent definitions and validate results but complete harmonization was not always possible.

Second, in order to create long-run series, covering multiple decades, a relative large number of data points had to be imputed. Data availability differs considerably between the two indicators and in time and space. While there is good coverage for high-income, Latin American and several African and central Asian countries, data availability is limited for other regions, resulting in a large share of imputed values. Further, in particular for the most recent period 2020-22, the number of imputed values is large. Overall, the coverage for the HR series is much lower than that for RD information. Users of GRAPE should be mindful of these limitations and be careful when using the database to study international public agricultural R&D trends. Future updates of GRAPE will modify these estimates as new data on public agricultural R&D becomes available.

The main data file includes two columns with codes that refer to the approaches that were used to handle extreme values and missing information in the raw data and the methods used to link information from various data sources, such as back- and forward splicing, and imputation. Table 2 and Table 3 present a brief explanation of the codes. By using these codes, users of GRAPE have the option to easily identify modifications to the raw data, remove adjusted observations in advance of statistical analysis or apply alternative imputation techniques to deal with missing information.

Table 2: Codes for quality control adjustments and treatment of missing data (step 2 in Figure 1).

Code	Description
none	No imputation, interpolation or data changes, excluding conversion to standard units (i.e. 2017 PPP\$ and FTE).
pa	Use of period averages for each individual year.
i_aux	Government and/or higher education series were imputed using the growth rate of an auxiliary data series (e.g. SEO-FORD or HR-RD series). EUROSTAT & OECD only.
ei	Interpolation of missing values using a constant exponential growth rate between two years.
adj	Adjustment of observation because of perceived data entry error.

Table 3: Codes for data linking and imputation approaches (step 3 in Figure 1).

Code	Description
none	No linking of data.
splice_new	Data was spliced together with more recent data series applying the growth rate for overlapping years.
splice_old	Data was spliced together with older data series applying the growth rate for overlapping years.
ei	Interpolation of missing values using a constant exponential growth rate between two years.
i_naive	Imputation using naive forecasting, i.e. carry the last observation forward.
i_ens	Imputation using an ensemble of imputed values - see GRAPE documentation for details.
i_man	Manual adjustment of imputed values - see GRAPE country documentation for details.

Code availability

Code was stored in a GitHub repository: <https://github.com/michielvandijk/GRAPE>. This includes R scripts to apply the imputation approaches to the pre-processed R&D statistics and convert R&D expenditure data in 2017 PPP\$, LCU and USD values. It also includes code to reproduce all the figures in this paper and the Supplementary Information.

Author contributions

M.v.D. and K.F. led the research; M.v.D., P.H. and K.F. proposed the generation of GRAPE and collected, harmonized and processed the raw data, partly building on earlier data collection efforts. H.D. collected and processed additional information for China. M.v.D. and K.F. curated the data and performed technical validation; M.v.D. prepared code to harmonize, process and combine the data; M.v.D. wrote the manuscript and database documentation with inputs from H.D., K.F. and P.H..

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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